

LIBRARY AS A LIVING SPACE REDEFINING STUDENT-CENTRIC DESIGN IN ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Libraries are often perceived as mere repositories of books and most people treat these structures as places to pass the time, rest, or escape the scorching heat. In addition, traditional libraries are underutilized as these places struggle to keep up with the rapid advancement of technology and being neglected by the society, as information can now be accessed anytime and anywhere with just a single click. This study examined the integration of biophilic design principles into the new campus library of Aldersgate College– Aurora Campus, aiming to redefine the traditional library function through innovative spaces that fosters interaction, collaboration, and intellectual growth. Embracing the natural beauty of the site, the design harmonizes natural elements mainly natural lighting and ventilation through its wide openings, and greenery to establish a connection between educational landscape and nature. Key strategies include flexible spaces designed both for learning and social engagement. The envisioned campus library enhances its traditional function as a storage of books, transforming into an inviting learning environment that nurtures curiosity and serves as a bridge to new ideas. In addition to key strategies, this study explored color theory within its spaces, the design stimulates students' curiosity while creating a more relaxing atmosphere, particularly in reading areas, where carefully chosen colors enhance focus, comfort, and engagement. This study highlights the potential of biophilic design to transform libraries into inclusive, and sustainable spaces, setting a new standard for educational institutions and serving as a model for future projects that integrate nature into the learning environment.

Keywords: Biophilic Design, Flexible Spaces, Color Theory, Learning Environment Interactive Learning, Campus Planning, Library Design

Introduction

Campus libraries in Philippine higher education serve a critical role in supporting students and faculty by providing essential resources for research, academic support, and knowledge acquisition. Despite this, a persistent issue lies in the perception of libraries as mere spaces to pass the time rather than hubs of intellectual growth (Dela Cruz, 2020; Reyes & Enriquez, 2021). This perception is exacerbated in the evolving educational landscape, particularly with the rapid shift to digital and online resources. As access to vast information becomes available at the click of a button, campus libraries are often underutilized due to end-users' lack of awareness regarding their services (Winter, 2017).

The development of Philippines libraries is influenced by Spanish colonial and American-era innovations, they also contribute to current limitations in awareness and utilization of library resources (Allaire et al., 2001). Additionally, issues such as insufficient funding, lack of expert guidance, and organizational support further compound challenges in effective library management (Fachrina Aprilia, 2016). Anon (2024) also notes that both students and faculty often lack time to engage meaningfully with the library, leading to inconsistent information literacy and underutilized services.

To counter this, campus libraries must be integrated thoughtfully into campus planning. As Ashikuzzaman (2024) emphasizes, strategic library placement can turn these spaces into central academic and social hubs, promoting collaboration, creativity, and intellectual exchange. Well-designed libraries should not only store books but also foster multifunctional, technologically integrated spaces that support research, collaboration, and cultural engagement.

Statement of the problem

The following problems are formulated to properly address these problems effectively:

- a. How can a college farm lot serve as a learning environment while also improving the educational status quo in the community?
- b. What design methods may be implemented to enhance the learning environment at the planned campus?
- c. In what ways might the campus be more efficient for its stakeholders?
- d. In what ways can a campus library be able to engage to its community through its spaces?

Objective of the Study

Campus Plan

The goal of the study is to design a general campus plan for Aldersgate College's New Campus located at Aurora, Municipality of Quezon.

- To Incorporate biophilic architecture in the planning and design approach.
- To design a campus layout that fosters community engagement through the shared spaces within.
- To conceptualize an integrated campus plan that effectively integrates passive, and active inclusive areas encouraging social interaction, physical activity, and leisure.

Campus Library

The project aimed to design and conceptualize a plan of a campus library for the new campus of Aldersgate College, Aurora, Municipality of Quezon. As sustainability is a given approach, to utilize renewable energy sources and efficient lighting systems, photovoltaic solar panels, rain water harvesting and using local construction materials. Overall creating a welcoming environment for the institutional community.

- To design a library for education, socialization, and recreation for its users.
- To implement flexible spaces and open-area layouts into interior designs, resulting in better adaptability and practical diversity in space utilization.
- To include biophilic elements such as open atriums for optimum natural lighting, plants, and a well-diversified reading place.
- To create spaces that include quiet reading nooks, group study areas, casual lounges, maker spaces, and café kiosks, all integrated with natural features like greenery.

Methodology

Research Design

By emphasizing data and resources, this research employed an applied approach to tackle and elaborate the challenges of a Semi-Agricultural Campus. The researcher identified key issues and proposed innovative solutions to develop sustainability, efficiency along with functionality within institutional environment.

Following that, the researched gathered data and information through ocular visits and direct communication with authorities involved. Upon gathering data, the feasibility was further studied in

order to proceed to the proposed solution. In addition, consultation from allied professionals was further executed.

To conclude, utilizing technical information collected from reliable sources, the researcher devised a strategy to apply the suitable design solution. This method verified that all data gathered during the study phase was reliable, and that all applicable legislation and legal requirements were followed.

Locale

location of the project is at Barangay Aurora, Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya. The area primarily consists of extensive agricultural land encircled by farming plots, with few to minimal residential buildings. A water feature such as a creek is also found within the location. Covering a total area of 13,906 square meters, this encompasses the entire Aldersgate College - Aurora Campus.

The site has been recognized as a viable option for an agricultural campus as it currently hosts rice and corn fields, making it an ideal location to establish a Semi-Agriculture Tertiary Educational Institution. Additionally, the site is in proximity to several educational establishments like Calaoan Elementary School, Cabinnuangan.

Research Participants

- The participants included in this study consisted the following:
- A** Aldersgate College Vice President of Administration, Engr. Josephine P. Jasmin, MBA, MEP-CE, who oversees all administrative matters of the mentioned college.
 - B** Aldersgate College Head of Planning and Development, Engr. Godofredo M. Batarao, Jr., RCE, RGE who is the main planner and engineer of the main campus of the said college.
 - C** Aldersgate College Aurora Campus Executive Designer, Engr. Angelito G. Capuno, RME, MBA who is responsible of the new campus and its infrastructure developments of the college in the municipality of Quezon.
 - D** Ms. Maybelle Blossom Dumlao-Sevillena, Quezon Municipal Planning and Development Officer who is responsible for managing and implementing infrastructure development and public works projects of the Local Government Unit of Quezon.

Research Instrument

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Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure would be employed to come up with an architectural design solution to existing problems stated by the proponent's, gathered data were elaborated and explained in the following.

1. Upon selecting the topic of the study, the essential details were introduced to the researcher's Adviser/promoter Ar. Tomas Binbinon Jr. This process gave us clarity and understanding that this present project was a continuation of the previous proposal of the new Aldersgate College, Aurora Campus. With the same goal in mind, the researcher's objective is to develop a campus plan for the institution as a Semi-Agriculture Tertiary Education.
2. The proponent and representatives, Aldersgate College Inc., and Engr. Godofredo M. Batarao, Jr., RCE, RGE, alongside with, Engr. Angelito G. Capuno, RME, MBA, who supplied site data and other important documents concerning the project. More information was obtained from various sources including books and the internet.
3. The researcher also conducted Case Studies from international related projects mainly (Edward S. Wolak Library, Chaffey College Library, Max Planck Institute Academic Library) and local (Aldersgate College Inc., Central Luzon State University).
4. After collecting all the necessary data for the study, the researcher examined and arranged the gathered data for application in the project's design.

Treatment of Data

The treatment of data included a detailed understanding, evaluation and derivation of the obtained data to initiated the architectural conceptualization and support the study objectives. This detailed analysis was critical in laying a firm foundation for architectural design, by methodically assessing the data, the study was able to identify applicable design principles, address critical obstacles, and construct a built environment that effectively addresses the specified demands and contextual elements. As this data analysis ensures that the proposed project leaves a big impact towards the needs and contribute in the wellbeing of its users.

Results and Discussions

The application of marketing ideas in semi-agricultural institutions enables the successful promotion of products, services, and academic programs. These institutions, which combine agriculture education with business and entrepreneurship, greatly benefit from smart marketing techniques. Programs frequently focus on agribusiness development, sustainable agricultural techniques, food production, and rural development, while also providing students with practical skills in market research, digital marketing, and branding. This hands-on experience teaches students how to promote agricultural advances in both local and worldwide markets.

As libraries at these semi-agricultural institutions expand their services and take on multifunctional responsibilities, they, too, may use marketing tactics to increase their influence. Libraries, formerly thought to be reservoirs of knowledge, are today transforming into hubs of learning, innovation, and institutional advancement. Libraries may improve their exposure, attract new users, and connect with the academic community by embracing digital platforms and marketing tools.

Lists of Plans, Elevations, Sections, and Perspectives

The following are the results of this study. These sections are the plans, elevations, sections, and views that illustrate the overall design solution used for the project.

Campus Plan

Figure 1
Proposed General Site Development Plan (No to Scale)

College Library

Figure 2
Right Wing Perspective

Figure 3
Facade Perspective

Figure 4
Ground Floor Reading Hall Perspective 1

Figure 5
Ground Floor Reading Hall Perspective 2

Figure 6
Flexible Events Place Perspective 1

Figure 7
Flexible Events Place Perspective 2

Figure 8
Main Lobby Perspective 2

Figure 9
Main Lobby Perspective 3

Figure 10
Science and Technology Section Perspective 1

Figure 11
Science and Technology Section and Carrel Perspective 2

Figure 12
Humanities and Social Sciences Section Perspective

Figure 13
Individual Carrel Perspective

Conclusion

The following are the objectives and problems issued described in the Chapter 2 of the study. These thorough conclusions outline the key concepts and strategies discussed in Chapter 3:

- The library serves as a multifunctional hub that balances academic development with opportunities for informal learning and relaxation.
- Modular furniture, convertible study areas, and open-plan reading zones enhance adaptability for various user needs and events.
- The Flexible and open-area Atriums, vertical gardens, daylight-optimized windows, and internal vegetation combine to provide a peaceful, nature-infused learning environment that promotes well-being and focus. These biophilic components help improve energy efficiency by optimizing natural light and airflow, making the room both environmentally friendly and inviting.
- The library employs a zoning system that smoothly integrates academic, collaborative, and recreational sections, each supplemented with biophilic design elements such as wood textures, natural ventilation, and living plants.

Recommendations

The researcher has identified important issues and developed design strategies to deal with them after thoroughly reviewing the data that was gathered. The following suggestions have been put forth upon consideration of the research's findings:

- To integrate smart lighting systems within the interior spaces of the library specifically on the reading areas.
- To integrate smart louvres in the façade of the building.
- To Install cloakrooms and enhance security by placing turnstiles at the library entrances.
- To provide shoe racks for the users going to the atrium carpet
- To redesign the existing breeze blocks to prevent rainwater from passing through.
- To include a refuge area in fire exits.
- To install canopies on each floor in the breeze block areas.

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